

A Study of Seagrass at Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve, Mississippi

Hyun Jung Cho, Jackson State University
Cristina Nica, Jackson State University

Seagrass beds provide nursery and foraging habitats for marine life, help improve water clarity, help reduce coastal erosion, and buffer wave energy. Therefore, temporal changes in their distribution and abundance indirectly reflect changes in the habitat quality and environmental health status. *Ruppia maritima*, the most abundant and common species in the Mississippi seagrass beds, is an opportunistic, pioneer species that is highly dependent on sexual reproduction. In order to provide information needed to identify areas that can support seagrass growth and to understand the temporal variations in the seagrass structures within the areas, we conducted biannual surveys at *Ruppia maritima* and *Halodule wrightii* beds in Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve (NERR), Mississippi. We hypothesized that there were significant spatial and short-term fluctuations in the coverage of *Ruppia/Halodule* beds. Three-way ANOVA was used to analyze seagrass depth distribution and abundance, which we surveyed along water depth gradients and shoreline orientation. Other pertinent water quality parameters - turbidity, [chlorophyll α], dissolved color, dissolved oxygen, pH, salinity, temperature, sediment, nutrients, and water level were monitored *in-situ* or obtained from the NERR monitoring data. The coverage and distribution of the beds dominated by *R. maritima* and the *Ruppia - Halodule* mixed beds of the tidal bay area (the estuarine area) in the reserve vary substantially primarily due to changes in *R. maritima* abundance between summer and fall. Our results on site variation in SAV coverage suggest that shore orientation and wind-driven energy within the estuarine system might be contributing factors to the spatial difference in the shallow estuary. The estuarine *Ruppia* population that grows in the shallow, high wave energy environment has an annual growth pattern: seedling growth in early spring, rapid vertical growth in April, producing abundant inflorescence and seeds in May and June, and senescence in the fall. On the other hand, *R. maritima* that occurs in the bayous and marsh in the reserve area, where tides and wind-driven wave actions are less severe, rarely flowers and sets seeds. Our results also suggest that consistent SAV survey efforts are needed to reduce errors in assessments of disturbance/restoration impacts and long-term trend, which will provide a useful tool for management and research.

Key words: Ecology, Water Quality, Wetlands

Introduction

Submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV) is a unique group of flowering plants that have adapted to live fully underwater. Seagrasses are the SAV species that are adapted to live in marine environment. Seagrasses represent critical ecosystems, with a much higher biomass compared to plankton-based oceanic communities, with relatively com-

plex physical structures. Seagrass beds provide combination of food and shelter that enables high biomass and productivity of commercially important fish species; an important nursery area for many species that support offshore fisheries and for adjacent habitats such as salt marshes, shellfish beds, coral reefs, and mangrove forests. Healthy seagrass beds also enhance shoreline stabilization:

the leaves of SAV reduce waves and currents; root and rhizome system bind sediments. Nutrient uptake and particulate sedimentation effectively improve water quality.

In Northern Gulf of Mexico, freshwater and brackish water SAV communities occur mainly in large, shallow bays and flats formed at the river mouths along the Gulf coast. Seagrasses, or salt water SAV species, are the most extensive SAV system in the area. There are a few species occurring in this region: turtlegrass (*Thalassia testudinum*), manatee grass (*Syrigodium filiforme*), stargrass (*Halophila engemania*), paddlegrass (*Halophila decipiens*), and Shoalgrass (*Halodule wrightii*). Wigeongrass (*Ruppia maritima*) has a broad salinity tolerance and also occur abundantly in the seagrass beds.

In the Mississippi Sound, seagrass beds had been declining more than 50 percent since the 1969 Hurricane Camille according to the early 1990's studies (Moncreiff, 2006). The more significant declines occurred in stable, climax community seagrasses such as *T. testudinum* and *S. filiforme*, which have resulted in the increased relative abundance of opportunistic species such as *R. maritima* and *H. wrightii* in estuaries and barrier islands of the northern Gulf of Mexico (Eleuterius 1987). The primary causes for this general decline in SAV habitat and the loss of species are likely water quality degradation and physical disturbances such as hurricanes. SAV distribution maps presented in the aforementioned reports and publications have been used as a critical indicator of the general long-term trends of SAV habitat in Mississippi Sound. However, seasonal and annual variations have become more pronounced in the Mississippi seagrass beds due the dominance of *R. maritima* (Cho and May 2008). *R. maritima* areal coverage and biomass are known to fluctuate considerably seasonally and annually elsewhere.

Objectives

The overall objective of this research is to develop an ecological model that links the spatial and temporal variability in the seagrass structure/competitive advantage with key environmental factors through a long-term study at the seagrass beds in

Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve (NERR). Our specific objective for this report was to identify the optimal growth conditions and areas for the seagrass species by studying temporal/spatial variations in the seagrass abundance, species composition, and biomass.

Methods and Materials

Biannual SAV survey

Five sites in Middle Bay, Jose Bay, Grand Bay of Grand Bay NERR were surveyed biannually (in July and in October) using transects since 2005. These sites represent gradients of species composition and abundance, shoreline type and aspect, shoreface slope (gradual—steep), and sediment composition, and tidal (or wave) fluctuation. At each site, we ran three 200-m transects perpendicular to the shoreline; and the each transect was surveyed by snorkeling and raking from a boat to record linear SAV coverage, species, density, and the corresponding depths. Water depth were calibrated to the mean water level; data were normalized whenever needed using appropriate data transformation methods. Differences in the SAV coverage (*Ruppia*, *Halodule*, mixed) were tested using ANOVA with fixed variables of season, year, and site.

Monthly SAV Biomass Sampling: Four replicates of core (an inside diameter of 7.5 cm diameter) samples were collected monthly at three of the sites: Middle Bay, Grand Bay, and Jose Bay. The samples were processed in a laboratory to assess seasonal, spatial (among sites and depths) variations in root (below-ground part) to shoot (above-ground part) dry biomass ratio.

Results and Discussion

Only two SAV species are currently present in the seagrass beds at Grand Bay NERR: *Ruppia maritima* and *Halodule wrightii*. The areal coverage and biomass of these two species change significantly monthly, between summer and fall, and annually (Figs 1 and 2). The temporal fluctuation is more prominent in *R. maritima* than in *H. wrightii*, but there is a general natural temporal cycle that can be induced from our datasets (Figs 1 and 2 and Table 1). In early spring, the *Ruppia* above ground

shoot biomass and coverage increase rapidly until they reach their maximum values in July (Figs. 1 and 2). Then the *Ruppia* population dwindles after reaching the maximum growth, the above ground biomass decreases rapidly in August (Fig. 2) and the areal coverage are reduced in the fall. Below ground biomass shows much less changes throughout the time period (Fig. 2), therefore, *Ruppia* shoot to root biomass ratios were as great as 13 in the spring and summer. This can partially explain the substantial annual variation in the summer *Ruppia* coverage (Fig.1) because we have observed the most significant loss of *Ruppia* shortly after severe spring and summer storms that uprooted the shallow-rooted SAV. The storm-related loss and recovery of above and below biomass have been documented elsewhere (Preen et al. 1995; Di Carlo and Kenworthy 2008). Unlike *R. maritima*, *H. wrightii* abundance showed much less temporal variations in their coverage. According to our ANOVA results (Table 1), *Halodule* abundance at a given site was not changed significantly among the years or even between July and October.

Despite the significant fluctuation in the coverage, species dominance, and biomass of the overall seagrass community in Grand Bay NERR, our study demonstrates that there are seasonal and annual biological cycles; and the unpredicted temporal/spatial variations probably are resulted by physical/chemical factors that interrupt the biological cycles. It is important to identify the key factors that prevent/limit SAV growth in the areas with no or less vegetation in order to set feasible restoration strategies and goals.

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Table 1. Results of a three-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to compare SAV coverage among survey sites, between two season (summer and fall), and survey years (2005-2008).

Source	P	
	<i>Ruppia maritima</i>	<i>Halodule wrightii</i>
Site	<0.001	<0.001
Season	<0.001	<0.001
Year	<0.001	<0.001
Site x Season	<0.001	0.572
Site x Year	<0.001	<0.001
Season x Year	<0.001	0.013
Site x Season x Year	<0.001	<0.001

Figure 1. Percent Transect Portion Covered by Seagrass. The white bars represent the *Ruppia maritima* coverage and the black bars represent *Halodule wrightii* coverage. The error bars represent standard errors.

Figure 2. Monthly mean below and above ground biomass of seagrass beds at three sampling sites in Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve. The error bars represent standard deviations.